

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DEFICIENCY RATE OF VITAMIN-D IN FEMALE HEALTH
CARE WORKERS OF FERTILE AGE**¹Hifza Habib, ²Muhammad Majid Kanwar, ³Moazmma Afzaal¹Rawalpindi Medical University and Allied Hospitals²Shifa Tameer E Millat, University Islamabad³Rawalpindi Medical University and Allied Hoapitals**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in healthy female health care workers of accouchement age.

Study Design: Cross-sectional descriptive study

Place and Duration of Study: This was conducted at the Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi from 1st july 2017_1st novemeber 2018

Materials and Methods: Two hundred and seventy healthy female doctors and nurses were recruited by random consecutive sampling. 25(OH) vitamin D and intact parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels were measured and effects of different variables were noted on vitamin D level.

Results: Three subjects out of 270 were excluded because of abnormal PTH levels. Median age was 28±4 years. Mean value of 25(OH) vitamin D was found to be 13.94±6.91. 254 (95.13%) were found to be deficient in vitamin D. Significant correlation was found between vitamin D deficiency and use of veil, obesity/malnutrition, married females, fish intake and lack of sun exposure.

Conclusion: Vitamin D deficiency has very high prevalence even in educated and relatively higher socioeconomic groups, even those having enough medical knowledge about its pathophysiology and effects.

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Please cite this article in press Hifza Habib et al., **Deficiency Rate of Vitamin-D in Female Health Care Workers of Fertile Age.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Bone mineralization is due to the Vitamin D which is a fat soluble vitamin. It is unique in that it cannot only be ingested in the diet as cholecalciferol (vitamin D3) or ergocalciferol (vitamin D2) but can also be synthesized in the skin when sunlight exposure is adequate. In spite of the binary operations of reification, vitamin D deficiency is common in many countries throughout the globe and can result in physical disorders and diseases. There are many roles of Vitamin D has in human body including calcium and phosphate homeostasis. As soon as absorbed from the stomach or induced in the skin, it is hydroxylated in the liver into 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D), then in the kidney and in extrarenal tissues to 1, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D) and 24,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (24,25(OH)₂D).

Subsequently, the active metabolite can pass into cells and mix with either the vitamin D-receptor or to a reactive gene, for instance, calcium binding protein. Therefore aids in calcium absorption [1]. Parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels are also regulated by Vitamin D which in turn lessen

Osteoporosis [2]. Severe vitamin D leads to new bone, the osteoid, not to be mineralized. This can result in rickets in minors and osteomalacia in adults. Inadequacy of Vitamin D has been linked with lesser BMD in people without frank osteomalacia [3,4]. It is not surprising therefore that in cases of severe vitamin D deficiency causing rickets or osteomalacia, a myopathy can develop and when severe, it presents with marked proximal muscle weakness with a predilection for the lower limbs [5]. Vitamin D has also recently been associated with many other conditions. Associations have been shown with colorectal cancer [6].

Thus, the active metabolite can pass into cells and mix with either the vitamin D-receptor or to a reactive gene, for instance calcium binding protein, and therefore aids in calcium absorption [1]. Parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels are also regulated by Vitamin D which in turn reduces bone loss [2]. Severe vitamin D deficiency causes new bone, the osteoid, not to be mineralized. This can result in rickets in minors and osteomalacia in adults. The deficiency of Vitamin D has been linked with lesser BMD in people without frank osteomalacia [3,4]. It is not surprising therefore that in cases of severe vitamin D deficiency causing rickets or osteomalacia, a myopathy can develop and when severe, it presents with marked

proximal muscle weakness with a predilection for the lower limbs [5]. Vitamin D has also been recently linked with many other conditions. Associations have been shown with colorectal cancer [6], diabetes mellitus, infection, multiple sclerosis, cardiovascular disease, breast cancer, autoimmunity and allergy [9], depression [10] and postural instability [11].

Foods which contain vitamin D include mackerel and salmon, fatty fish like tuna, foods fortified with vitamin D, like some dairy food, soy milk, orange juice and cereals, egg yolks and beef liver cheese.

There are many reasons of the deficiency of the vitamin D. Mainly these can be divided into two classes: Medical/physical condition-related deficiency and UVB-related deficiency. UVB-related deficiency is found in the elderly^{12,13} dark skin people [14], sunscreen users [15] and also depends upon season, latitude and the time of day. Medical conditions causing vitamin deficiency include fat malabsorption [16], chronic kidney disease [17], obesity [18] and drugs like anticonvulsants [19].

The aim of our study was to highlight the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in a cohort of women of child bearing age and correlate them to certain demographic variables. Most of the published literature on Vitamin D levels in Pakistanis performed in smaller outpatient settings, involving low socioeconomic groups of the population. There is a dearth of published data on prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in asymptomatic population of middle and high socioeconomic group like health care workers including female doctors and nurses and to highlight importance the lack of awareness even in medical field workers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The cross-sectional study was conducted at Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi from 1st July 2017-1st September 2018. The sample size was calculated to be 270 assuming an anticipated population proportion of 85%, a relative precision of 0.05 with 95% confidence. Healthy adult female doctors and nurses, without any comorbidity, aged between 18 years to 45 years, were recruited by non-probability random consecutive sampling and informed consent was taken. Subjects who had vitamin D supplementation in last 6 months were excluded. Data was recorded on a predesigned Performa including demographic and socioeconomic details, BMI, marital status,

lactation status, number of children, exposure to sun light, milk intake, veil usage, fish intake, water source and any history of musculoskeletal problems.

Venous blood samples of 10 ml were collected by trained health care workers in plastic serum tubes for each respondent. The samples were put in ice boxes at the location of the camp and were sent to the lab in collections. There was a time gap of approximately 60 minutes between venous puncture and serum separation after centrifugation at 3000 bpm. After centrifugation the serum was stored in the laboratory freezer at -20°C , until further analysis. Serum markers measured included 25(OH) vitamin D, intact parathyroid hormone (PTH) measurements. Vitamin D deficiency was taken as 25-hydroxyvitamin D blood level below 30 ng/ml and severe deficiency was defined as 25-hydroxyvitamin D blood level below 20 ng/ml.

Levels above 75 ng/ml were taken as toxicity. The data was entered and analyzed in SPSS v17. Explanatory statistics were calculated and effect of different factors on vitamin D level was analyzed.

RESULTS:

The sample comprises of 270 females of child bearing age. 267 subjects' data was analyzed further. Median age was 28 ± 4 years. 3 females were excluded from the results because of abnormality in intact PTH level. The minimum age reported in the sample was 23 years with a maximum age of 45 years. Mean value of 25 (OH) vitamins D was 13.94 ± 6.91 . Only 13 (4.87%) subjects had the level in sufficient range, i.e., ≥ 30 ng/ml. Rest of the sample population which is 254 (95.13%) were found to be deficient in vitamin D. Demographic, social and behavioral determinants of vitamin D status in healthy adult females are described in table 1.

Table No.1: Demographic, social and behavioral determinants of vitamin D status

Determinant Factor	Subgroups of Determinant Factor	Mean 25(O) vitamin D level $\pm$ SD	p- value
Age	18-30	16.94 $\pm$ 6.91	<0.05
	31-45	12.94 $\pm$ 3.81	
BMI	<18.5	10.24 $\pm$ 2.71	<0.05
	18.5-24.9	18.33 $\pm$ 6.13	
	>25	14.34 $\pm$ 3.54	
Marital status	Single	19.94 $\pm$ 5.61	<0.05
	Married	13.25 $\pm$ 5.32	
Lactation status	Lactating	17.94 $\pm$ 5.91	>0.05
	Non lactating	18.34 $\pm$ 6.91	
Children	Yes	13.72 $\pm$ 4.81	>0.05
	No	15.64 $\pm$ 7.31	
Exposure to sun light	<30 min	11.54 $\pm$ 4.22	<0.05
	≥ 30 min	22.64 $\pm$ 7.32	
Use of veil	Yes	11.94 $\pm$ 3.52	<0.05
	No	16.94 $\pm$ 6.71	
Daily milk intake	Yes	18.74 $\pm$ 2.64	>0.05
	No	17.98 $\pm$ 3.42	
Fish intake	Yes	19.56 $\pm$ 6.96	<0.05
	No	16.31 $\pm$ 3.91	
Water source	Tap	14.94 $\pm$ 5.11	>0.05
	Boiled	14.74 $\pm$ 6.83	
	Mineral	17.94 $\pm$ 6.91	
Open space in home	Yes	16.33 $\pm$ 7.41	>0.05
	No	14.44 $\pm$ 3.93S	
Monthly income	<10000	14.94 $\pm$ 2.61	>0.05
	10000-30000	15.54 $\pm$ 4.33	
	>30000	16.48 $\pm$ 1.95	
H/O musculoskeletal problem	Yes	10.94 $\pm$ 3.95	<0.05
	No	18.94 $\pm$ 2.81	

DISCUSSION:

Our study found very high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency in Pakistani female population which is consistent with reported values of vitamin D deficiency in a few earlier studies carried out in Pakistan [20-22].

Significant correlation was found between vitamin D deficiency and use of veil, obesity/malnutrition, married females, fish intake and lack of sun exposure, keeping in view with other studies [23]. Milk intake was not significantly related to vitamin D deficiency in our study. It has also been reported previously that serum calcium does not predict serum 25(OH) D levels [24]. Also it has been noted that vitamin D deficiency becomes more severe with advancing age [25] and it was also the case in our study.

Unique point in our study is that it estimated the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in an educated and relatively good socioeconomic status population. Apart from this, the study population was healthy adult health care worker females, doctor and nurses who are supposed to have education about high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency. It was found that an alarming 95% of them are deficient in vitamin D.

CONCLUSION:

Very high rates of vitamin D deficiency among healthy female doctors and nurses of a tertiary care hospital and showed that even health care workers need awareness about alarming levels of vitamin D deficiency, probably due to changing life styles. It is recommended that women who are not in a position to increase their sun exposure can significantly reduce their risk of vitamin D deficiency by taking a multivitamin tablet containing vitamin D.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest to declare by any author.

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